

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue II, February 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

+639985799958

*"Write. Connect.
Educate."*

 @pinagpalapublishing

 pinagpala_publishing

 www.pinagpalapublishing.com

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue II (Feb. 2024) / International Circulation

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678 / Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

The Education in a New Chapter

Ryann Christoper G. Hermoso, MAEd

Teacher II

Bartolome Sangalang National High School

Region III

It's almost the end of the academic year 2019-2020 where all of the stakeholders celebrate the success of the students' hardships, sacrifices of the parents, and teachers but in January 2020 the first case of COVID-19 was declared and recorded in our country. Since then, a number of cases arises, the government imposed a temporary locked down in the middle of March 2020.

It caused many impacts in various aspects of the country. The education sector was one of the affected departments. I recall being in a private school during that time. A bell rang unusually and announces the cancellation of classes due to the risk of COVID-19. We, teachers and students, were shocked but teachers started to packed up paper works that can be done in-home during the said weeks. However, the two weeks have been abruptly extended for two months. Administrators, instructors, students, and parents immediately altered how meetings were handled. It transitioned from a face-to-face situation to a digital context.

Not everyone can use gadgets or control software programs. Previously, some exclusively used Facebook Messenger to interact with friends and relatives, but when Covid-19 assaults, many electronic programs have been utilized for meetings because of its convenience to connect with co-employees. Despite possessing laptops, smartphones, and other gadgets, internet connectivity became also a challenge. Different telco firms provide load, data, and connections; however, communication is hampered due to the community's remote satellite. It's been a major adjustment for everyone. Everything went digital all of a sudden. Distance learning was once only available through higher education institutions, but it is now used by the Department of Education. Since we are in a third-world country, there has been a rapid transformation in Philippine education. The transition from daily reporting to the school to alternating work arrangements was a big one. Previously, seminars were held in person, but this has evolved to webinars, which are held online. Teachers are primarily interested in teaching in a four-corner classroom, but they are now teaching at home and conducting virtual classes using a variety of online platforms. Furthermore, educators are not limited to utilizing a single platform for teaching and learning because students can choose any modality they like. Modular print, modular digital, online learning, blended learning, and the use of televisions and radios as supplemental material are all possible. Teachers, particularly experienced teachers, grew more and were willing to learn and use new technologies and software programs to create learning management systems. One thing is

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue II (Feb. 2024)/ International Circulation

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

that teaching computations with traditional chalk and board is difficult—in the past, teachers used chalk and chalkboards, but now the virtual whiteboard is being used similarly to a jam board.

The finest teacher is experienced. Students can use their knowledge and science skills in laboratory lessons, which makes teaching them fun. However, because of the pandemic, access to the wet laboratory has been restricted, and performing laboratory experiments has been prohibited. However, technology is always advancing, which is why a dry laboratory is currently used.

People all over the world are run by technology. While technological advancements have made countries safer and our lives easier, they have also harmed our lives. Due to technology, our lives become better and more convenient. Before libraries are just contained in a room but now it becomes digital where you are able to access them online. It gives a new face because of technology.

Teachers cannot be replaced by technology at this time of pandemic because they can download, use, and manipulate it. It shows that teachers are not only good in traditional teaching but better teachers in a new way of educating students.

Despite its status as a third-world country, the Philippines' education sector faces pandemic-related problems in maintaining its ability to provide high-quality education. It only proves the saying that “Nothing can be a hindrance to education and to the better future of the youth of this nation.”

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10714855

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.